

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract

Digital transformation refers to integrating digital technologies into all aspects of an organization's operations, fundamentally changing its functioning and customer values. It involves the use of digital tools and technologies, such as cloud computing, data analytics, artificial intelligence, automation, and the Internet of Things (IoT), to streamline processes, improve decision-making, improve customer experience, and increase innovation.

Keywords: Digital transformation, management, growth, efficiency

Introduction. The impact of digital transformation on organizational management is profound and long-lasting. The use of digital technologies increases efficiency and productivity because they automate repetitive tasks and streamline workflows by reducing manual processes. This increases efficiency and productivity. Managers allocate resources more efficiently, streamline operations, and focus on strategic initiatives that drive growth.

Discussion. Improved decision-making: Digital transformation involves access to real-time data and advanced analytics tools that enable managers to make data-driven decisions. They can analyze trends, identify patterns, and gain insights into customer behavior, market dynamics, and operational performance, which enables managers to make more informed decisions and deliver better results.

Agility and Adaptability: Digital transformation enables organizations to be more agile and adaptable in response to market conditions, customer preferences, and competitive pressures. Managers can quickly change strategies, shift priorities, and experiment with new approaches to stay ahead and seize opportunities.

Improved Customer Experience: Digital technologies allow organizations to personalize customer information to the fullest. Managers can use data analytics and a variety of customer relationship management (CRM) systems to better understand customer needs and behaviors to deliver personalized products, services, and interactions that lead to satisfaction and loyalty, as well as greater trust, which is a guarantee of loyalty.

Innovation and Creativity: Digital transformation fosters a culture of innovation and creativity in the organization's internal processes. Managers will use digital tools and collaborative platforms to encourage idea-sharing, experimentation, and the development of new products, services, and business models that create value and drive growth.

Organizational Resilience: Digital transformation enhances organizational resilience through remote work, virtual collaboration, and business continuity planning. Managers can leverage cloud-based technologies, digital communication tools, and cybersecurity measures to mitigate risks, ensure operational continuity, and adapt to unforeseen disruptions such as natural disasters or global pandemics.

Talent Management and Leadership: Digital transformation creates new skills and competencies for employees, as well as leadership that is optimized for digital alignment, or better yet, maximizes employee support for digitization. Managers should invest in development, skill development, and initiatives to grow a digital workforce that can implement innovative ideas and compete in a digital world.

Overall, digitalization has a major impact on organizational management, requiring managers to adopt new technologies, adapt to practice, increase their drive for innovative ideas, and continuously improve their performance in a digital and competitive business environment.

Digitization is the process of converting analog information, usually represented as binary code (0 and 1), into a digital format that can be processed, stored, and transmitted electronically. This process involves capturing, encoding, and storing data in digital form, allowing it to be accessed and shared more efficiently than other similar analog formats.

Digitization generally involves:

- **Analog data capture:** Digitization begins with the capture of analog data from physical sources, such as paper documents, photographs, audio recordings, or video footage. This may involve scanning or recording analog information using digital devices such as scanners, cameras, or microphones.

- **Encoding and digitizing:** Analog data is encoded and converted into digital format using algorithms and encoding techniques. For example, text documents are created into machine-readable text using

optical character recognition (OCR), while images and videos can be digitized using image or video compression algorithms.

- Digital data storage and management: Once digital data is digitized, it is stored and managed in digital repositories such as databases, file systems, or cloud storage platforms. This allows for easy access, retrieval, and manipulation of data using digital tools and technologies.

- Digital data processing and analysis: Digital data can be processed and analyzed using software applications, algorithms, and analytical tools to extract information, identify patterns, and derive meaning from the data. This includes data mining, statistical analysis, machine learning, or artificial intelligence techniques.

- Digital content sharing and dissemination: Digital content can be easily shared and disseminated across digital networks and platforms, enabling widespread access and dissemination of information at a rapid pace. This facilitates collaboration, communication, and knowledge sharing among individuals and organizations.

Digitalization has brought about many changes across sectors. It has transformed the way information is received, understood, and used, leading to increased efficiency, innovation, and connectivity in a digital world.

Digitalization has a profound impact on companies and their outcomes, for example: Digitalization improves processes, streamlines tasks, and reduces manual intervention, which increases efficiency and productivity. Companies can complete tasks faster with fewer resources, leading to cost savings and better bottom-line results.

Digitalization allows businesses to provide personalized and comprehensive information about their customers. From online shopping and self-service facilities to mobile apps and social media, digitalization ensures that businesses can engage with customers on their terms, leading to higher satisfaction, trust, and retention.

Digitalization generates a vast amount of data that companies can use to study and understand customer behavior, market trends, and operational performance. By processing this data and using analytical techniques, companies can make better-informed decisions, uncovering maximum opportunities.

Digitalization fosters a culture of innovation and agility in companies through several examples and

iterations like this. Companies can quickly adapt to changing market conditions, customer variability, and competitive threats, which allows for more time to market and greater responsiveness to challenges.

Digitalization allows businesses to reach international markets and expand their long-term plans more easily than under traditional conditions. With digital platforms and online marketplaces, companies expand their customer base, enter new markets, and grow without the need for different physical infrastructure or resources.

Digitalization leads to cost reductions through process optimization and resource consolidation. At the same time, it opens up new revenue channels through digital products, services, and business models. Companies can disrupt data, offer subscription-based services, and create digital multi-functional systems that generate recurring revenue and other opportunities.

Digitalization also enhances the operational state of remote work. Through online collaboration and business continuity planning, companies can use cloud computing, digital communication tools, and cybersecurity measures to mitigate invisible risks, ensure operational continuity, and adapt quickly to unforeseen disruptions, such as global pandemics.

By digitalizing, companies can generate more innovation, improve efficiency, and achieve sustainable growth in today's global economy.

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